

The influence of high preloading forces on the behaviour of the bolt in ring flange connection

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ABSTRACT

Ring flange connections with preloaded high-strength bolts are commonly used to connect segments of tubular steel towers supporting wind turbines (WT). The performance of a bolt in a flange connection is crucial for ensuring the structural integrity and reliability of cyclically loaded towers. The behaviour of the ring flange connection is dominantly influenced by the geometry of the connections and accomplished pretension force in bolts, and bolt grade. According to IEC 61400-6, the design pretension force of the bolt is limited to 70% of the yield strength of the bolt. This rule exists in EN1993-3-1-8, and it is imposed to limit the size of plastic strain regions. The plastic strains firstly appear in the threaded part of the bolts, in contact with a nut. In this numerical study, the influence of high preloading forces on the behaviour of ring flange connection is presented. The experimental results and a finite element analysis are compared on a flange segment using M56 bolts, ISO nuts and washers to validate the numerical model. The effect of the preloading on three key aspects: plastic strain distribution, deformation capacity, and a shell(tower)-to-bolt transition function are presented in the paper.

Keywords: Ring flange connection, Bolt resistance, Preloading force, Deformation capacity, Fatigue assessment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ring flange connections are widely used to connect segments of tubular steel towers supporting wind turbines. The connections are executed with prestressed, high-strength bolt assemblies and are commonly subjected to high cyclic loads with very large number of cycles of variable amplitudes. The fatigue failure of bolts may lead to the failure of the supporting tower for WT. The fatigue life of bolts depends on many factors, including coating [1], the geometry of the thread [2], the manufacturing process [3], the presence of defects [4], and the level of preloading [5].

According to Tower and Foundation Design Requirements IEC 61400-6 [6], the design pretension force of the bolt is limited to 70% of the yield strength of a bolt. Prestressing above the bolt's average yield strength is permissible only if considering the plastic deformation capacity of the bolt. It is important that bolts are preloaded with as high forces as allowed according to design standards and with an accurate pretension technique to reduce the fatigue stress amplitudes in the bolts. However, high preloading forces, especially when preloaded beyond its yield strength, result in gross yielding of the bolt in combination with localized yielding at the threads due to the notch effect. Mean stress fatigue models for bolts rolled after heat treatment showed that the fatigue strength depends upon mean stresses. Higher average mean stresses lead to reduced fatigue resistance. The reason behind this phenomenon is attributed to the relaxation of beneficial compressive residual stresses which are initially introduced by rolling. However, when the mean stress increases, it causes localized plasticity in the material. This localized plasticity leads to the reduction of the compressive residual stresses, ultimately decreasing the fatigue resistance of the bolts[3,5].

In contrast to bolts manufactured by rolling before heat treatment, the results of experiments show that the fatigue strength is independent of mean stresses [16]. Stephens et al. [3] experimentally investigated the fatigue behaviour of rolled before and after heat treatment bolts under five preload levels varying from 1% to 100% of the proof stress. The test results revealed that the fatigue strength decreases as the preload level increases for the two types of thread manufacturing. Similar findings are observed in [7].

This emphasises the importance of investigating the influence of high preload forces on the behaviour of the bolt in the ring flange connection to ensure the expected safety of cyclically loaded structures. In this paper, a parametric study is carried out on an advanced validated numerical model of the ring flange connection with M48 bolts to evaluate the influence of higher design preload bolt forces than those proposed in the IEC standard on the plastic strain distribution in the bolt, deformation capacity, and the shell-to-bolt transition function.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

2.1 Model characteristics

The ring flange segment is modelled in ABAQUS 2021 software package [15] to predict the behaviour of the segment. To ensure that the Finite Element (FE) models built for the study are reliable and can provide valuable results, the experimental results obtained from a test campaign at the Stevin laboratory in TU Delft on the L-flange segment with M56 bolt were analysed. This test is a representative case for validating the model's performance and accuracy. Figure 1-a illustrates a schematic representation of the segment, but the absolute dimensions cannot be provided due to the project's confidentiality constraints. The M56 partially threaded bolt and nut are modelled with threads featuring a tolerance class of 6g and 6h, respectively, according to ISO 965-1 [8]. In addition, ISO 7090 [9] washers are modelled.

Regarding the material properties, elastic properties are assigned to the washers, with elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio taken as $E = 210$ GPa and $\nu = 0.3$, respectively. Elastic-plastic properties are assigned to the segment, bolt, and nut, see Figure 1-a. The segment is made of steel grade S355. The nominal stress-strain curve with a bilinear hardening material model is utilized for the segment. The stress-strain curve of the 10.9 grade bolt and the nut with a non-linear hardening model is assumed and the ductile damage model is used to model the failure of the bolt according to [10]. The engineering stress-strain curves for the different parts are converted into the true stress-strain curves for input into the ABAQUS plasticity model, see Figure 1-b.

Fig. 1. a) L-flange connection model. b) True stress-strain curve of segment, bolt, and nut.

For the analysis, the explicit solver is employed. The first defined step is the preloading of the bolt, which is achieved by the turn-of-nut method. The hexagon edges of the nut are coupled to a reference point located at the centerline of the nut. A rotation of 3.7 radians is applied to turn the nut to achieve a preloading force of 1290 kN, as shown in Figure 2-a, while keeping the rotation of the bolt head fixed. This preloading force is the final measured force after the preloading losses. In the second step, the external load is applied in terms of displacement to a reference point coupled to the top surface of the shell. All the degrees of freedom are restrained at the bottom surface of the shell. The mesh used for the bolt, washers, and nut consists of quadratic tetrahedral elements (C3D10M) and with an element size of 5 mm. The flanges are meshed with eight-node hexagonal elements (C3D8R) with reduced integration and hourglass control, and an element size of 7 mm. The meshed geometry of the L-flange is shown in Figure 2-b. General contact interaction with tangential behaviour ‘penalty’ and a friction coefficient of 0.14, along with hard contact for the normal behaviour, is employed.

Fig. 2. a) Turn-of-nut method for preloading. b) Boundary conditions and meshing.

2.2 Model Validation

The experimental test on the segment was conducted under quasi-static loading up to 1000 kN to determine the load transfer function (LTF) and evaluate the strains in the flanges and shells. Several measurements were recorded during the test including the gap opening, as well as the strains on the shell and the flange. The gap opening is measured using a linear variable differential transformer (LVDT), mounted on the sides of the flange to monitor the displacement of the flange contact surface, also known as the gap, during loading. A schematic view of the instrumented measurements is presented in Figure 3. The strains and gap are extracted from the FE model at the location where the measurements are taken and compared with the experimental results. The FE strains in the shell are extracted at the location where strain gauge 1 is positioned, whereas the extracted FE strains in the flange are compared with the results measured by strain gauge 3. The FE displacement of the flange contact surfaces is compared with the gap measured by LVDT1. Moreover, the bolt force is extracted from a free body cut at the threaded section to construct the LTF against the applied external load.

Fig. 3. The instrumented measurements on the segment.

In Figures 4-a – 4-d, the experimental and the FE results are compared. It can be observed that the FEA results exhibit very good agreement with the experimental results. For comparison, the results at an external load of 800 kN are evaluated. The bolt force shows a difference of 4%, while the measured gap has a difference of 8%. Similarly, differences of 5% and 10% are found in the strain of the shell and flange, respectively.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the FE results with experimental results. a) load transfer function; b) displacement of the flange contact surfaces (gap); c) strains in the shell; d) strains in the flange.

3 PARAMETRIC STUDY OF PRELOADING

Three L-flange segment models with M48 bolts are built to investigate the influence of the high preloading forces on the bolt stiffness, plastic strain distribution, and a shell-to-bolt transition function. The geometry of the L-flange segments employed for the parametric study is outlined in Figure 5. In accordance with the validated model, the same material properties for the bolt, nut, and segment are utilized. Moreover, the same type of analysis, external load application on the shell, mesh pattern, and interaction properties are applied. The turn-of-nut method is applied to achieve the targeted preloading force. Three preloading forces are analysed, corresponding to 70%, 90%, and 100% of the tensile area of the bolt (1473 mm²) multiplied by its yield strength of 900 MPa. The targeted preloading force is achieved by adjusting the nut rotation for each case, as listed in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Geometry of the segment.

Table 1. Rotation of the nut and the corresponding preloading force.

Average preloading	Nut rotation [rad]	Preloading force [kN]
70%	1.4	928
90%	2.4	1190
100%	3	1325

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Plastic strain distribution

Currently, the design requirements specify to 70% of the bolt's yield strength. To achieve a higher level of preload than the specified design recommendations, it is essential to ensure sufficient plastic deformation capacity in the bolt. The strain distribution along the bolt cross-section for the different preloading levels is shown in Figure 6. All cases show a non-uniform strain distribution along the bolt section. The highest strains are observed in the vicinity of the thread root. As the preload increased, an expansion of plastification is observed in the bolt cross-section. In the case of 70% preloading, it can be seen that the strain at the thread roots exceeds the elastic strain (f_y/E) equal to 0.00428, while the bolt core remains in the elastic zone. On the contrary, at 90% and 100% preloading, the bolt is fully plastic, and the strains extracted along the section are in the plastic zone. A minimum strain of 0.59% is found for 90% preloading, whereas a significantly higher strain of 2.3% is found for 100% preloading. It should be noted that bolt threads are formed by rolling. This manufacturing process entails significant plastic deformation at the thread root, resulting in the formation of microcracks which cannot be fully prevented [4]. In addition, existing material flaws and inclusions may also be present causing higher local plastic strains at the thread root. The high plastic strains

from high preload levels (90% and 100%) in combination with the local plastic strain from defects at the thread root result in a substantial reduction in the fatigue strength, whereas plastic strains in components should be limited to maintain the structural integrity of the connection.

4.2 Deformation capacity

The deformation capacity of the bolt for the various cases is calculated by averaging the strains along the section at the first engaged thread between the bolt and nut, see Figure 6. The obtained mean strain is compared to the strain at fracture. The mean percentile strain $\bar{\epsilon}$ is 0.49, 0.78, and 2.9 for 70%, 90%, and 100% preloading, respectively. As per ISO898-1 [11], the nominal strain at fracture (ϵ_t) for full-size 10.9 fasteners equals 13%. This leads to deformation capacities ($\bar{\epsilon}/\epsilon_t$) of 26.5 and 16 for 70%, and 90% preloading, respectively. At 100% preloading, a value of 4.5 is found which is almost 20% of the deformation capacity of the bolt. In contrast, when the bolt is preloaded with 70%, the bolt still has sufficient deformation capacity after preloading, which is almost 96% of the total deformation capacity. In other words, a discernible reduction of 83% in deformation capacity is observed when the preload increases from 70% to 100%.

Fig. 6 Strain distribution in the bolt subjected to; a) 70% preloading; b) 90% preloading; c) 100% preloading.

4.3 Shell-to-bolt transition function and fatigue life of the bolt

Bolts in wind turbines experience significant cyclic loads characterized by a substantial number of load cycles and varying amplitudes. For the fatigue limit state, the determination of the exact bolt force as a function of the applied external load is crucial. The shell-to-bolt transition function for different preload levels is shown in Figure 7. It can be observed that the curve for the highest preload, 100% preloading, has the flattest shell-to-bolt transition function. This is mainly attributed to the high pressure acting in the contact zone between the flange which is overcome at high external loads. For the bolt, this results in low variation in stresses, e.g. reduced fatigue load ranges and consequently improved fatigue performance. Table 2 presents the stress range in the bolt ($\Delta\sigma_b$) for different preload levels at an external load range (ΔF) of 200 kN, with a maximum force of 600 kN and a minimum of 400 kN. This is equivalent to an external stress range on the tower segment of 37 MPa. The fatigue life of the bolt is assessed based on the experimentally derived mean S-N curve for M48 bolts [12], as shown in Figure 8. The fatigue life of the bolt with 100% preload increased 29 times that of the bolt with 70% preload. However, imperfections due to uncertainties in the manufacturing process such as inclinations or gaps between the flanges cannot be avoided [13]. These imperfections can significantly influence the actual load in the bolts, leading to high variation in the bolt stresses. This poses a risk to the connection with 100% preloading when subjected to high cyclic loads, given that the preloading force level is close to the ultimate capacity of the bolt. Also, it should be noted that a 90% preload is applied to permanent connections [14].

Fig. 7 Shell-to-bolt transition function for different preload levels

Table 2. The stress range and the fatigue life of the bolt for different preload levels.

$\Delta F = 200 \text{ kN} \sim \Delta\sigma_{\text{seg}} = 37 \text{ MPa}$		
Preloading	$\Delta\sigma_b$ [N/mm ²]	N_f [Cycles]
70%	146	1.4×10^5
90%	79	8.5×10^5
100%	51	4×10^6

Fig. 8 Test results for hot-dip galvanized HV M48 bolt and fatigue strength curves of EC 3 and static evaluation for the 50 % quantile of the survival probability [8]

5 CONCLUSION

This numerical study is carried out using the validated FE model of the L-flange connection with M48 bolt. The influence of higher design preload bolt forces than proposed in the IEC standard on the plastic strain distribution in the bolt, deformation capacity, and the shell-to-bolt transition function are investigated. The analysis of strain distribution along the bolt cross-section revealed that when the bolt is preloaded till its yield limit, high plastic strains, with a mean strain of 2.9%, are predicted in the bolt. The combination of these (by high preload force induced) plastic strains and potential defects at the thread root may result in a reduction of fatigue strength. Additionally, the deformation capacity of the bolt decreased by 83% when the average preload level increased from 70% to 100%. Finally, the flattest shell-to-bolt transition function was found for the highest preloading reducing the fatigue loads on the bolt. The fatigue life of the bolt with 100% preload increased 29 times that of the bolt with 70% preload. Still, inherent imperfections in the manufacturing process of flanges and bolts introduce imperfections. These imperfections may negatively influence bolt stress amplitude when exposed to high cycle loads. It is especially problematic when the preloading force is close to the ultimate resistance of the bolt, which risks the structural integrity of the connection.

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